

ISic3100

I.Sicily inscription 3100

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI331426

1. [— — — — —]ΕΠΑΙΣ [— — — — —]
2. [— — ὑπ(ατία) τῶν] κυρίων ἡμ [ῶν Ὀνωρίου τὸ ιγ']
3. [καὶ Θεοδο]σίου τὸ ι [— — — — —]
4. [— — — — —]
- 5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645448

PHI 331426

Bibliography

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